

Agai, Lapai, Kasha, Mokwa, and Pateggi were surveyed (523 fields). Ricefields were examined at 9 spots (the four corners, midway along each edge, and at the center).

During 1985-87 cropping seasons, BI occurred most frequently. It affected rice at all stages of development and was most severe on late-planted seedlings.

Other fungi diseases observed, in order of prevalence, were brown spot [caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan]; leaf scald [*Gerlachia oryzae* Has. and Yokogi]; glume discoloration (many pathogens); sheath blight [*Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn]; stem rot [*Sclerotium oryzae* Catt]; sheath rot

[*Sarocladium oryzae*]; bakanae [*Gibberella fujikuroi* (Sawada), Ito]; false smut [*Ustilagoidea virens* (Cke) Tak]; and narrow brown leaf spot [*Cercospora oryzae* Miyake].

Rice yellow mottle virus and unconfirmed bacterial blight symptoms were found occasionally. □

Insect management

Incidence of rice stem borer (SB) in the Punjab

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We surveyed incidence of rice SB *Scirpophaga* spp. and *Sesamia* spp. in the Punjab. Samples of rice stubble were collected at harvest from 98 locations in 1986 and from 60 locations in 1987 and dissected to determine tiller infestation and larvae/hill.

Overall tiller infestation was 25% in 1986 and 18% in 1987 (see figure). Traditional rice-growing Kalar tract and Ahmad Nagar were badly infested; Gujarat, Mandi Bahauddin, and Sheikhupura were comparatively less infested.

SBs found were yellow rice SB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Wlk.), white SB

Incidence of rice SB in the Punjab, 1986-87.

S. innotata (Wlk.), and the pink graminaceous SBs *Sesamia inferens* (Wlk.) and *S. uniformis* (Dudg.).

Scirpophaga spp. made up 357 of 362 larvae collected in 1986, and 1,291 of 1,296 larvae collected in 1987. □

Whitefly (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) - a potential pest of rice in West Africa

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Whiteflies are pests of many crops and also vectors of several plant virus diseases. Whiteflies on rice were first reported in 1966, when *Aleurocybotus indicus* D. and S. was identified in Satara, India. In 1970, *Bemisia tabaci*

M. and H. was found on rice in Madras, India.

A. indicus was reported to be restricted to India, with its preferred hosts graminaceous grasses *Chloris barbata* and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*. But *A. indicus* was reported in Africa in April 1977, on irrigated rice at Richard Toll, Senegal. In recent years, it has spread to Mauritania, Senegal, Burkina Faso, Nigeria, and Niger.

The insect attacks rice plants from seedling to flowering stages. During the hot, dry season, especially in Feb, Mar,

and Apr, the insect is seen in irrigated rice at the IITA experimental farm at Ibadan. It has become a serious problem in screenhouses and insect rearing cages. When infestation is high, black sooty mold that develops on rice leaves can cause withering and plant death.

In the course of screening for *Diopsis longicornis* in the screenhouse, we found no *Oryza sativa* or *O. glaberrima* varieties that were tolerant of whitefly (500 entries tested).

A calcid larval parasite, *Encarsia* sp. found at Ibadan is definitely not